

STUDY OF MACROBENTHOS OF PONDS OF SASARAM WITH SPECIAL EMPHASIS TO POSSIBILITIES OF FISH CULTURE

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Abstract

The ponds under investigation of Sasaram namely Sher shah suri tomb Pond, Amra talab, and Salim Khan pond are very old ponds and have historical value. The ponds were constructed with an idea to water harvest the rainwater for agricultural and domestic purposes. In the long run when population has increased the periphery of the water bodies has inhabited by dense population and releases the untreated waste in the water bodies leading to eutrophication of the pond , dense algal bloom etc. due to negligence of the people the beautiful ponds are polluted and not even used for the benefit of the local person . There is no scientific fish culture in the ponds for economic and employment gain. The nutritional status of the pond soil i.e pH (7.1-8.0) slightly alkaline. The value of soil Nitrogen (520.0-978.1mg/kg) Phosphorus 11.2-17.4mg/kg) Potash (103-501mg/kg.) and organic carbon % of the pond(2.1- 4.08%) keeps the ponds under productive categories. In totality, water temperature depends on geographical location and climatic conditions such as, rainfall, humidity, cloud cover etc. The air temperature of the three ponds under investigation 24.43 ± 5.3 and water temperature 24.68 ± 5.24 . the pH was 8.1, Dissolved oxygen 6.7ppm, free carbondioxide 16.1 ppm, total alkalinity 199 ppm, Conductivity 2.44, transparency 30.9 cm, BOD 0.28ppm, and plankton 0.28 ml/50 lits of water. The ponds are not under any commercial use of fish culture though it has got potentiality and can bring the income and employment in the area through fish culture. The fish species may stocked as per the primary productivity of the ponds for utilization of fish culture which will also improve the water quality.

KEY WORDS: pH, air temperature, eutrophication

INTRODUCTION

Macrobenthic communities are the organisms that live on, or in the bottom of the water body. The benthic animals are extremely diverse and are represented by all phyla from protozoans, through large macro invertebrates to vertebrates. The diversity and abundance of benthic fauna are most frequently used in biomonitoring studies because they significantly respond to various organic and inorganic pollution . Extended residency period of various macrobenthic communities in specific habitats and presence or absence of particular benthic species in a particular environment can be used to group them as bio-indicators of specific environmental & habitat conditions. These benthic organisms contribute a lot to the food chain, as after their death and decay they are used by aquatic plants and other animals.

Invertebrate communities change in response to changes in physicochemical factors and available habitats. The biotic structure and water quality of streams and rivers reflect an integration of the physical, chemical and anthropogenic processes occurring in a catchment area, leading to the concept of ecological integrity. Human induced hydrological changes, physical disturbances (habitat alteration, urban land use) and point and nonpoint sources of pollution (chemical contamination, surface runoff, intensive agriculture) are examples of processes responsible for a broad-scale deterioration of lotic and lentic ecosystems . The abundance of benthic fauna greatly

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depends on physical and chemical properties of the substratum. Benthic macro-invertebrates can be used as a barometer of overall biodiversity in aquatic ecosystems. Macrobenthic invertebrates are a ubiquitous and diverse group of long lived species that react strongly and often predictably to human influences in aquatic ecosystem. Macrobenthic invertebrates are an important and integral part of any aquatic ecosystem as they form the basis of the trophic level and any negative effects caused by pollution in the community structure can in turn affect trophic relationships. These can include those that feed on them directly or indirectly such as fish and bird populations, respectively. In addition, aquatic invertebrates have the ability to clean water as they utilize the organic and detritus matter. According to Carlisle et al. (2007) macro invertebrate populations in streams and rivers can assist in the assessment of the overall health of the stream. Biological assessment and criteria can be used as the basis for management programs, restoring and maintaining the chemical, physical and biological integrity of freshwater. Live organisms offer valuable information regarding their surrounding conditions and can be used to evaluate the physical, chemical and biological impact and their cumulative effects (Karr and Chu, 1999). In addition, surveys of the richness and species composition, the relative abundance of groups or species and the feeding relationships between the inhabiting organisms are the most direct measure to determine if a water body meets the biological standards for aquatic life. Realising their immense importance, several workers have attempted to study the diversity of macrobenthic invertebrates in aquatic ecosystem in lotic and lentic water bodies.

Agricultural, industrial, household, recreational, environmental activities use fresh water resources for healthy development of human civilization. Fresh water resources are actually very precious for the life on our planet. The number of dams, reservoirs, tanks, etc. has significantly increased in last few years. The development of fisheries in these fresh water resources is the present need using scientific techniques. Limnological investigations on water bodies were generally analyzed to determine the pollution level of the water bodies time to time. The abiotic and biotic factors of the water influence the quality and quantity of aquatic life surviving there. The role of water in nature is unique not only for human; but, also for the numerous organisms living in the water. The physical and chemical properties of fresh water bodies are characterized by the climatic, geochemical, geo morphological and pollution condition. In order to utilize fresh water bodies successfully for fish production, it is very important to study the Physico-Chemical factors influencing the biological productivity in the water bodies (Sahni and Yadav, 2012). The quality of aquatic life surviving in the pond is totally dependent on the water quality of the pond. In the recent years several studies have been made in this field (Yadav *et al.*, 2013) not much information is available on Physico- Chemical and biological parameters of the present water bodies. Physicochemical parameters and aspects pertaining to these ponds used for culture of fish are not available. Hence the present work is an attempt to study the detailed information on some important Physico-Chemical and biological parameters of the rural ponds of Sasaram of Bihar.

Sasaram is located at 24.95°N 84.03°E. It has an average elevation of 200 m (660 ft). It is surrounded by hills from two sides and so the climate of Sasaram is seasonable (means in winter it is too cold and in summer it is too hot). Climate is characterized by relatively high temperatures and evenly distributed precipitation throughout the year. The climate is Humid Subtropical Climate.

Sasaram has its historical importance it is the birthplace of the Afghan king Sher Shah Suri, who ruled over Delhi, much of northern India, what is now Pakistan, and eastern Afghanistan for five years, after defeating the Mughal Emperor Humayun. After his death, he was followed as king by his son Islam Shah, then Adil Shah, and finally by the Hindu king Hemu, or Hem Chandra Vikramaditya. Many of Sher Shah Suri's practices were adopted by the Mughals and the British Raj including taxation, administration, and the building of a paved road from Kabul to Bengal.

Sher Shah Suri's 122 feet (37 m) red sandstone tomb, built in the Indo-Afghan style stands in the middle of an artificial lake at Sasaram. It borrows heavily from the Lodhi style, and was once covered in blue and yellow glazed tiles indicating an Iranian influence. The massive free standing dome also has an aesthetic aspect of

the Bhuddhist stupa style of the Mauryan period. The tomb of Sher Shah's father Hasan Khan Suri is also at Sasaram, and stands in the middle of green field at Sherganj, which is known as Sukha Rauza.

Shershah was born (1486 AD) in Sasaram, Bihar. His original birth name was Farid Khan. Later on, he was known as Sher Khan (The Lion King) after he killed a full-sized tiger (Sher) with his bare hands and then he was called Sultan-E-Azam Sher Shah Suri (The Great Lion Emperor Shershah Suri). Shershah was a visionary ruler and a brilliant strategist, as he proved himself a gifted administrator as well as an able general. He was a great Indian-born Afghan ruler and ruled Bihar and much of the Northern subcontinent including Delhi and remains a hero to Pathans across India, Pakistan and Afghanistan. Shershah was the world widely credited personality. During his short five year rule from 1540 AD to 1545 AD, he set up a new template

for civic and military administration and he minted three currencies, termed the Rupiya (that are still used for the national currency in Pakistan, India, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Indonesia, Mauritius, Maldives, Seychelles), Mohur and Dam. He built the longest highway of the continent of Asia popularly known as "The Grand Trunk Road" and also re-organized the postal system of India.

Selected Pond for the present study was constructed by Shershah Suri (1538 AD). At the centre of the pond a mausoleum was built in the memory of Emperor Shershah Suri by the architect Aliwal Khan (1540 to 1545 AD). This red sandstone mausoleum is known as the second Taj Mahal of India. This magnificent mausoleum is one of the noblest specimens of Pathan architecture in India. Its dome rising is more than 135 feet and covers the second highest in India. The tomb is remarkable for its sober style, its artistic setting in a tank, and its elegant kiosks grouped round the grand dome to relieve the severity of the composition. The tomb was completed after his death (May 22, 1545 AD) by his son sultan Salim Shah and Islam Shah Suri in AD 1545. For the present study, it is significant that the pond was constructed 470 years ago and now it is going to be recognized as world heritage site because of its historical importance. During the present investigation it was observed that quality of water has been extremely changed and now pond has become a highly eutrophic in nature .

Material & Methods

The Physico chemical parameters of all the ponds were monitored on monthly basis as per standard methodology. The soil analysis was done on half yearly basis. (APHA, AWWA, WPCF, 1981).the macro benthos were collected with the help of ekman's dredge on seasonal basis.

Results & Discussion

The soil analysis of three pond is presented in the Table -1. The observation revealed that the pH was alkaline ranging from 7.1 to 8.0. The phosphorus ranges 11.2 mg/Kg to 17.4mg/kg, potash 103mg/kg to 501mg/kg Nitrogen 520mg/kg to 978.1mg/kg and Nitrogen 520.08 mg/kg to 978.1mg/kg. the organic carbon percentage was 2.1 to 4.0.

Table 1: Soil analysis of the pond

Pond	N (mg/kg)	P (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)	O C%	pH
Sher shah suri Tomb pond	520.08	14.9	351.9	2.179	7.1
Amra talab	978.1	17.4	501.0	4.080	7.5
Salim khan talab	721.6	11.2	103.0	3.010	8.0

The physico chemical parameters of the three pond recorded in table 2-7 represent that the air temperature ranges from 16.2 to 34.5⁰c. Whereas water temperature varied from 19.4 to 31.5⁰c. The pH of the water varied from 7.4 to 9.6. The dissolved oxygen concentration varied from 5.0 ppm to 9.8 ppm. The free carbondioxide

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concentration was recorded 14 ppm to 22 ppm. The biological oxygen demand was 13.2 to 26.4 ppm. The total alkalinity varied from 188 ppm to 220 ppm . The conductivity varied from 2.1 to 2.82 . The transparency varied from 28.0 cm to 35.7 cm and plankton concentration was 0.2 to 0.4ml.

Table:2 Physico-chemical parameters of Sher Shah Suri Tomb pond

Month	Air temp. (°C)	Water temp. (°C)	pH	DO (ppm)	CO ₂ (ppm)	Total alkalinity (ppm)	Conductivity (m ^{sc} m ⁻¹)	Transparency (ppm)	BOD (ppm)	Plankton concentration (ml)
October`11	21.0	24.5	7.6	6	20	202	2.82	36.0	14.8	0.3
November`11	17.2	26.7	7.5	6	22	216	2.74	33.2	15.8	0.3
December`11	22.4	24.2	7.4	6.4	20	210	2.60	32.6	16.2	0.4
Jan`12	16.2	19.4	7.6	8	16	196	2.3	29.5	19.2	0.3
Feb`12	18.4	21.6	7.6	7.6	20	190	2.34	30.5	19.4	0.4
March`12	24.5	25.2	7.9	6.4	14	180	2.4	30.1	20.2	0.4
April`12	29.5	27.5	8.2	6	10	188	2.5	29.5	23.8	0.4
May`12	31.0	34.0	8.5	5.6	8	188	2.66	29.2	25.8	0.3
June`12	30.5	34.5	8.6	5.6	8	186	2.68	29.	26.2	0.3
July`12	29.0	27.0	8.1	6.4	10	186	2.7	30.2	24.4	0.3
August`12	27.0	25.4	8.0	6	12	192	2.8	34.0	20.4	0.2
September`12	26.5	28.4	7.8	5.6	18	196	2.8	26.0	18.6	0.2

Month	Air temp. (°C)	Water temp. (°C)	pH	DO (ppm)	CO ₂ (ppm)	Total alkalinity (ppm)	Conductivity(m ^{sc} m ⁻¹)	Transparency (ppm)	BOD (ppm)	Plankton concentration (ml)
October`12	21.8	24.6	9.1	9.1	20	206	2.74	34.4	16.8	0.3
November`12	17.5	22.5	9.2	9.2	22	220	2.61	32	15.4	0.3
December`12	22.6	21.5	9.3	9.8	20	202	2.54	31.8	14.4	0.3
Jan`13	17.0	20.2	9.2	9.2	18	198	2.22	28.3	16.8	0.2
Feb`13	18.0	22.5	8.5	8.5	22	193	2.26	29.4	15.4	0.3
March`13	24.5	26.1	8.5	8.5	16	184	2.32	29.1	17.4	0.3
April`13	29.0	28.4	8.7	8.7	12	192	2.41	28.3	19.4	0.2
May`13	31.5	35.0	8.8	8.4	12	192	2.56	28	20.4	0.2
June`13	30.5	35.2	8.1	8.1	10	186	2.64	28.8	23.4	0.3
July`13	29.5	28.6	8.1	8.1	12	186	2.67	29.1	24.6	0.2
August`13	27.5	26.8	8.0	8.0	14	194	2.71	32.4	20.0	0.2
September`13	26.8	25.5	7.8	7.8	18	199	2.70	34.1	20.2	0.2

Table: 3 Physico-chemical parameters of Amra talab

Month	Air temp. (⁰ C)	Water temp. (⁰ C)	pH	DO (pp m)	CO ₂ (ppm)	Total alkalinity (ppm)	Conductivity(msc m ⁻¹)	Transparency (ppm)	BOD (ppm)	Plankton concentration (ml)
October`11	21.0	2.5	7.9	7.2	16	210	2.68	34.1	11.4	0.4
November`11	17.2	26.7	7.8	7.2	20	214	2.60	31.3	11.8	0.3
December`11	22.4	24.2	7.6	7.6	22	218	2.30	31.4	10.6	0.2
Jan`12	16.2	19.4	7.8	7.6	20	201	1.98	29.8	10.4	0.2
Feb`12	18.4	21.6	7.9	7.2	18	198	2.2	30.1	10.2	0.3
March`12	24.5	25.2	8.1	6.8	16	194	2.36	29.8	18.6	0.3
April`12	29.5	27.5	8.4	6.4	16	190	2.4	29.4	18.4	0.3
May`12	31.0	34.0	8.5	6.4	14	190	2.42	29.1	19.8	0.2
June`12	30.5	34.5	8.7	6.0	10	194	2.5	28.9	18.6	0.2
July`12	29.0	27.0	8.4	5.6	12	192	2.6	29.7	17.8	0.2
August`12	27.0	25.4	8.2	5.6	16	188	2.66	33.1	16.4	0.4
September`12	26.5	28.4	8.0	6.8	14	204	2.66	34.2	16.8	0.4

Month	Air temp. (⁰ C)	Water temp. (⁰ C)	pH	DO (pp m)	CO ₂ (pp m)	Total alkalinity (ppm)	Conductivity(msc m ⁻¹)	Transparency (ppm)	BOD (ppm)	Plankton concentration (ml)
October`12	21.8	24.6	8.4	6.4	18	214	2.40	34.9	16.8	0.3
November`12	17.5	22.5	9.2	6.4	20	216	2.28	31.5	15.8	0.3
December`12	22.6	21.5	9.3	6.8	22	220	2.16	31.6	17.4	0.3
Jan`13	17.0	20.2	9.4	7.2	22	202	2.1	30.1	19.8	0.2
Feb`13	18.0	22.5	8.6	6.8	20	200	2.14	30.8	19.4	0.2
March`13	24.5	26.1	8.7	6.4	18	192	2.28	30.1	21.8	0.3
April`13	29.0	28.4	8.8	6.0	18	194	2.36	30.4	22.2	0.3
May`13	31.5	35.0	8.3	6.4	16	188	2.28	29.8	22.4	0.2
June`13	30.5	35.2	8.1	6.0	16	196	2.42	29.4	17.8	0.2
July`13	29.5	28.6	8.1	5.6	14	202	2.50	29.9	17.2	0.2
August`13	27.5	26.8	7.9	5.6	14	198	2.54	33.6	16.4	0.3
September`13	26.8	25.5	8.2	6.0	18	210	2.52	34.8	16.6	0.3

Table: 4 Physico-chemical parameters of Salim khan talab

Month	Air temp. (⁰ C)	Water temp. (⁰ C)	pH	DO (pp m)	CO ₂ (ppm)	Total alkalinity (ppm)	Conductivity(ms cm ⁻¹)	Transparency (ppm)	BO D (pp m)	Plankton concentration (ml)
October`11	21.0	24.5	8.6	6.4	20	202	2.72	35.2	17.6	0.2
November`11	17.2	26.7	8.8	6.4	22	212	2.68	32.1	19.4	0.2
December`11	22.4	24.2	8.9	6.8	20	216	2.50	31.5	20.0	0.2
Jan`12	16.2	19.4	9.1	7.6	18	198	2.20	29.1	24.6	0.2
Feb`12	18.4	21.6	9.2	7.2	16	192	2.24	30.1	24.4	0.3

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March`12	24.5	25.2	9.3	6.8	14	190	2.3	29.9	25.0	0.3
April`12	29.5	27.5	9.4	6.4	16	192	2.4	29.5	26.4	0.4
May`12	31.0	34.0	9.5	6.4	14	188	2.56	29.1	24.8	0.3
June`12	30.5	34.5	9.3	5.6	12	188	2.58	28.8	20.8	0.2
July`12	29.0	27.0	8.7	5.6	12	194	2.60	29.9	14.8	0.3
August`12	27.0	25.4	8.5	6.0	16	196	2.7	33.1	14.6	0.3
September`12	26.5	28.4	8.4	6.0	18	188	2.72	35.2	13.2	0.2

Month	Air temp. (°C)	Water temp. (°C)	pH	DO (ppm)	CO ₂ (ppm)	Total alkalinity (ppm)	Conductivity(ms cm ⁻¹)	Transparency (ppm)	BOD (ppm)	Plankton concentration (ml)
October`12	21.8	24.6	8.7	6.0	18	204	2.68	35.7	14.8	0.2
November`12	17.5	22.5	8.8	6.4	22	214	2.40	32.0	15.6	0.2
December`12	22.6	21.5	8.9	6.4	24	218	2.32	30.5	16.4	0.2
Jan`13	17.0	20.2	9.3	7.2	22	220	2.18	28.4	19.4	0.2
Feb`13	18.0	22.5	9.4	6.8	18	194	2.2	29.1	20.0	0.2
March`13	24.5	26.1	9.5	6.4	16	192	2.28	28.8	22.0	0.3
April`13	29.0	28.4	9.7	6.0	18	194	2.36	28	26.0	0.2
May`13	31.5	35.0	9.4	6.0	16	190	2.46	28	26.4	0.2
June`13	30.5	35.2	9.5	5.6	18	190	2.48	28.5	18.8	0.3
July`13	29.5	28.6	8.8	5.6	14	196	2.52	29.3	18.8	0.2
August`13	27.5	26.8	8.6	5.2	14	198	2.54	34.2	16.8	0.2
September`13	26.8	25.5	8.5	5.2	16	190	2.62	35.8	16.2	0.2

Table: 5 Relative abundance of Macro invertebrate species recorded from the pond

Sl.no	Macro-invertebrate species recorded from the ponds	Relative abundance		
		Pond-1	Pond-2	Pond-3
Annelida				
1	Aulodrilus americons (Brink)	-	-	+
2	Branchura somerbyl (Badd.)	-	+	+
3	Bratylavia bilongata(Echan.)	+	-	++
4	Chaerogaster sp.	-	-	++
5	Dero pectinata(Clap)	-	-	+
6	Dero obtuse(Ayier)	-	-	+
7	Lymnodryllus udekemias(Clap)	-	-	+
8	Lymnodryllus claparidianus (Clap)	-	-	+
9	Potamothrion vejelovesky (Har.)	+	+	+
10	Tubifex tubifex (Miller)	++	++	++
Insecta				
1	Arisopetera sp.	+	+	+
2	Berosus sp.	+	+	+
3	Chironomus sp.	++	++	++
4	Dineutus sp.	++	++	++

5	Glyptotendips	+	+	+
6	Gyrinus sp.	+	+	+
7	Orthocladius sp.	+	+	+
8	Tabenus sp.	+	+	+
9	Tanipus sp.	+	+	+
Mollusca				
1	Gibba obscura(Neuill)	+	+	+
2	Gyraulus convexiculus(Hulfan)	+	-	+
3	Indoplonorbis exustus (Deshyayi)	+	-	+
4	Lymnea accuminata (Gray)	+	+	+
5	Thira scabra(Muller)	+	+	+
6	Thira tuberculata(Muller)	+	+	+
7	Viviparous beglensis(gauld)	+	+	+

Table: 6 Relative abundance of Phytoplankton species recorded from the pond

Sl.no	Phytoplankton species recorded from the ponds	Relative abundance		
		Pond-1	Pond-2	Pond-3
Chlorophyceae				
1	Pandorinia sp.	+	++	++
2	Ankistrodemas sp.	++	+	++
3	Pediastrum sp.	+	++	+
4	Spirogyra sp.	+	+	++
5	Kireherinella sp.	++	++	++
6	Eudorira sp.	+	++	+
7	Chorella sp.	+	+	++
8	Chlosterium sp.	++	++	++
9	Seenedesmus sp.	+	+	+
10	Cosmarium sp.	++	++	++
Myxophyceae				
1	Oscillatoria sp.	+	+	++
2	Cylindropermum sp.	+	+	++
3	Merismopaedia sp.	+	++	+
4	Mycrocystis sp.	++	++	++
5	Spirulina sp.	+	+	+
6	Anabaena sp.	++	++	++
7	Phomedium sp.	+	++	++
Bacillariophyceae				
1	Navicula sp.	+	+	+
2	Surinella sp.	+	+	+
3	Melosira sp.	+	+	+
4	Cyciotella sp.	+	+	+
5	Nitzschia sp.	+	+	+
6	Synedra sp.	+	+	+
7	Fragellaria sp.	+	+	+
8	Asterionella sp.	+	+	+
9	Stephanodiseus sp.	+	+	+
10	Euglena sp.	+	+	+
11	Lyphosyneles sp.	+	+	+
12	Phacus sp.	+	+	+

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Table: 7 Relative abundance of Zooplankton species recorded from the pond

Sl.no	Zooplankton species recorded from the ponds	Relative abundance		
		Pond-1	Pond-2	Pond-3
Protozoa				
1	Verticella sp.	+	+	++
2	Ceratium sp.	+	+	+
3	Peridinium sp.	-	++	++
Rotatoria				
1	Bracionus sp.	+	+	++
2	Keratella sp.	+	+	++
3	Filinia sp.	+	+	+
4	Asplachna sp.	-	++	++
5	Polyarthra sp.	+	+	+
Lalodocera				
1	Moina sp.	++	++	++
2	Ceriodaphnia sp.	++	++	++
3	Chydorus sp.	++	++	++
4	Daphnia sp.	++	++	++
5	Bosmina sp..	++	++	++
Copepoda				
1	Menocyclops sp.	+	+	++
2	Microcyclops sp.	+	+	+
3	Heliodiapiomus sp.	+	+	+

Soil nutrient is the important factor for the pond productivity. pH of the soil is considered one of the single important factors affecting pond productivity. It not only influence the soil microbial activity but also affect the availability of nutrients to pond water - either native or when applied externally. The availability of native or added phosphorus greatly influenced by soil reaction. In acid soil phosphorus fixed or rendered unavailable as iron and aluminium phosphate and in alkaline soil as calcium phosphate (Banerjee & Ghosh, 1970). Banerjee and Mondal (1965) have shown that the concentration of added phosphate decline rapidly in acidic, neutral and alkaline soils and the rate of decline in phosphate concentration had shown a significant relationship with the composition of the soil. Like phosphorus the response of different nitrogenous fertilizers depend on soil reaction.

Saha (1969) observed that loss of added nitrogen is minimum with ammonium form in acid and neutral soils and with nitrate form in alkaline soils. Calcium ammonium nitrate, urea and ammonium sulphate were found to be more effective in enhancing primary production, survival and growth of carp fry for moderately acidic, slightly acidic to neutral and alkaline soils respectively (Saha et al., 1975). In general slightly acidic to slightly alkaline soil pH is considered favourable for productivity. In the present investigation all three ponds were alkaline.

The various basic elements (carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, iron, sulphur etc.) needed for the existance and nutrition of biologically productive organisms in aquatic environment are obtained from the soil and atmosphere for the enrichment of pond water. Among these elements nitrogen, phosphorus carbon and potassium are of importance compared to calcium, magnesium, iron sulphur etc. Nitrogen, being a basic and primary constituent of protein and chlorophyle, is necessary for the formation of living matter in a large quantity.

Phosphorus is required in smaller quantity compared to nitrogen, it is considered as the single critical element for maintaining aquatic productivity. Phosphorus takes part in all aspects of cellulose metabolism, synthesis of protein and growth. Potassium helps in the formation of protein, chlorophyll and also stimulates the growth of aquatic flora. The atmosphere is the main source of inorganic carbon required for photosynthesis, thus converting the inorganic carbon to organic, while the decomposition of soil organic matter by microbial activity converts organic carbon to inorganic carbon and acts as a source of energy for microbial action.

Nitrogen in soils is present mostly in organic forms which are broken down into simpler inorganic compounds through bacterial action. Due to unlimited supply of this element from the atmosphere through fixation by azotobacter, blue green algae and atmospheric electric discharge, the deficiency of this element is less acute compared to phosphorus deficiency, usually encountered in most soils.

Potassium due to its easy availability in pond soil and water is not found to be limiting productivity.

The role of organic carbon (OC) in maintaining the productivity of fish ponds is well recognized. Apart from influencing various physico-chemical properties of bottom soils and releasing different nutrient elements to more available forms in the pond environment, it controls an important property of the pond eco-system viz. oxidation-reduction reaction (Mandal and Chattopadhyay, 1992).

On the basis of above observations by different workers the nitrogen is 520mg/kg to 978mg/kg so the ponds falls under high group. The potassium ranges between 103mg/kg to 501mg/kg so it keeps the ponds under high productive group. The organic carbon % ranges 2.1 to 4.08 so it falls under high productive group of pond.

Temperature is a physical factor that alters the water characteristics and considered as an important factor in controlling the fluctuation of plantation and functioning of aquatic ecosystem. In the present investigation seasonal variability of atmospheric and water temperature have been observed. It was maximum during summer comparatively less during monsoon and minimum during winter. Kannan and Job (1980) also found similar results as observed in the present study.

The turbidity of a body of water is related to the cleanliness of the water. Waters with low concentrations of total suspended solids (TSS) are clearer and less turbid than those with high TSS concentrations. Turbidity can be caused by high concentrations of biota such as phytoplankton, or by loading of abiotic matter such as sediments. Turbidity is important in aquatic systems as it can alter light intensities through the water column, thus potentially affecting rates of photosynthesis and the distribution of organisms within the water column. Lowered rates of photosynthesis may in turn affect the levels of dissolved oxygen available in a given body of water, thus affecting larger populations such as fish. High turbidity can also cause infilling of lakes and ponds if the suspended sediments settle out of the water column and are deposited.

Turbidity measurements can be used for water quality analysis in lakes and streams. Generally the more turbid a lake is, the less biota it will be able to support. Turbid waters inhibit light from penetrating deeply into water column and therefore negatively affect primary productivity and dissolved oxygen available to support other organisms.

Water transparency is an important factor that controls the energy relationship at different trophic levels. The results of transparency ranged between 25 cm. to 60 cm. during the study period.

Welch (1952) states that the limnological value of pH is a limiting factor and works as an index of general environmental condition.

The pH value of the pond showed alkaline trend with a few variations. The maximum pH value were in the month of April i.e. 9.4 and minimum in the month of October i.e. 8.88. It is evident from the data that the pH declines during

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the rainy and increases during summer. Sharma *et al.*, (1984) states that in India, many small confined water pockets are particularly alkaline in nature Seasonal fluctuations are small indicating good buffering capacity

Oxygen content is important for direct needs of many organisms and affects the solubility of many nutrients and therefore the periodicity of aquatic ecosystem (Wetzel, 1983). Fritsch (1907) stated that the oxygen contents in tropical water would be low considering their high temperature. The results of the present study showed that highest peak value of dissolved oxygen was recorded during the month of January i.e. 10.50 mg/l and least in the month of June i.e. 5.15 mg/l.

The value increased from July to January and then decreased from February to June. Results of the present study are similar to those reported by other (Prasad *et al.*, 1985; Hulyal and Kaliwal, 2011; Ramulu and Benarjee, 2013).

Alkalinity in most natural water is the function of bicarbonate and carbonates. Their salts get hydrolyzed in solution and produced hydroxyl ion. It is also used as a measure of productivity (Jhingran, 1982; Hulyal and Kaliwal, 2011).

Natural water bodies in tropics usually show wide range of fluctuations in their total alkalinity value depending upon the geography and season. In the present study the total alkalinity ranged between 418.25 to 583.01 mg/l. It is gradually decreased from July to September and then increased in the month of October reaching to 549.90 mg/l again followed by a decrease in November and December. Seasonally highest value was recorded during rainy and lowest during the summer season. Increases in total alkalinity during rainy season were due to input of water and dissolution of calcium carbonate ion in the water column (Padma and Periakali, 1999). The degradation of plants and other organism and organic waste might also be one of the reason for the increase in carbonate and bicarbonate thereby the alkalinity (Jain *et al.*, 1997; Chaurasia and Pandey, 2007).

Electrical conductivity of the water depends on the nature and concentration of salts in high ionic concentration, pollution status, trophic levels, some domestic effluents and other organic matter in water (Ahluwalia, 1999).

The range of electrical conductivity in the present study was between

2.4 mScm-1 to 2.9mScm-1. The values of electrical conductivity showed marked seasonal variation being maximum during rainy and minimum during winter season.

Similar results were observed by various workers (Hulyal and Kaliwal, 2011; Ramulu and Benarjee, 2013).

The biochemical oxygen demand determination is a chemical procedure for determining the amount of dissolved oxygen needed by aerobic organisms in a water body to break the organic materials present in the given water sample at certain temperature over a specific period of time.

BOD of water or polluted water is the amount of oxygen required for the biological decomposition of dissolved organic matter to occur under standard condition at a standardized time and temperature. Usually, the time is taken as 5 days and the temperature is 20°C. Ordinary domestic sewage may have a BOD of 200 mg/L. Any effluent to be discharged into natural bodies of water should have BOD less than 30 mg/L. Drinking water usually has a BOD of less than 1 mg/L. But, when BOD value reaches 5 mg/L, the water is doubtful in purity. Jain and Dhanija (2000) have considered BOD as an important parameter in aquatic ecosystem to establish the status of pollution. The observation of present study the ranges were ranges from 13.2 ppm to 26.4 ppm highest value during rainy season and lowers during winter season. There was variation in pond 1 and pond 2 & 3 may be due to the waste matter flowing in the pond from the catchment. Seasonally, the BOD was highest during late summer /early rainy season. High BOD during late summer / early rainy season may be due to the presence of

several microbes in water bodies which accelerate their metabolic activities with the increase in concentration of organic matter in the form of municipal and domestic waste pouring into the pond with run off. Prasanna Kumari et al., (2003) also stated that the higher values of BOD during rainy was also due to input of organic wastes and enhanced bacterial activity.

High temperatures do play an important role by increasing rate of oxidation. The BOD of unpolluted water is less than 1.00 ppm moderately polluted water 2.00-9.00 ppm while heavily polluted water have BOD more than 10.00 ppm. The BOD in different season in the present study indicates pond as moderately polluted.

Plankton are the microscopic organisms that drift on the water currents. Phytoplankton forms the sole base of food chain in aquatic system as they act as energy transducers and convert the solar energy into chemical energy of food. Zooplankton passes this food energy to the higher trophic levels and thus provides a link between energy producers and the consumers. These organisms are important biological indicator of water quality and trophic status of aquatic ecosystem as they respond quickly to the environmental changes.

Phytoplankton is the pioneer of an aquatic food chain. Biological production can be used as an index of trophic status and fisheries resource potential in any aquatic body (Jhingran, 1992). The productivity of an aquatic environment is directly correlated, with the density of phytoplankton (Narasimha, 2013) as they play an important role as primary producers and thus can affect higher trophic levels by providing nutritional bases for zooplankton and subsequently to other invertebrates, shell fish and finfish (Emmanuel and Onyema, 2007).

The zooplankton in Indian water bodies consists of diverse assemblage of major taxonomic groups. Many of these forms have different environmental and physiological assemblage. The number, type and distribution of these organisms present in any aquatic habitat provide a clue on the environmental condition prevailing in that particular habitat. It is seen that many environmental factors interact to provide conditions for the growth of zooplankton both spatially and seasonally (Khanna *et al.*, 2009). According to Trivedy and Goel (1984).

Maximum zooplanktons were observed in winter probably due to low temperature, high content of DO and low velocity (Khanna *et al.*, 2000; Khanna and Bhutiani, 2003; Purushothama *et al.*, 2011).

The plankton concentration varied from 0.1 to 0.3 ml/25 l of water. It was more in winter season and low in summer season. All the ponds are rich in phyto plankton concentration. the chlorophyceae comprises 34% , Myxophyceae 24%, Bacillariophyceae 42% of the total phyto plankton population

The zooplankton concentration was low protozoa comprise 19%, Rotatria 31%, Copepoda 19% and Lalodocera 31%. The zooplankton concentration is low for commercial fish culture (Jhingran, 1982). The high concentration of phytoplankton is due to heavy organic carbon load in the pond, this also support the moderately polluted pond.

The abundance of benthic fauna mainly depends on physical and chemical properties of the substratum. Further, benthic communities are known to respond to changes in the quality of water or habitat. Because of their extended residency period in specific habitats and presence or absence of particular benthic species in a particular environment these can be used as bio-indicators of specific environment and habitat conditions.

It is interesting to note that the biodiversity of macrobenthic fauna in three ponds 26 species were found. Most dominant benthic species encountered were *Berosus sp.* *Chirononus* larvae, *Glyptotendips sp.* *Dineutus sp.* *Thiratuberculata*, *Viviparous beglensis* ,*Bratilavia bilongata*,*Chaerogaster sp.tubifex sp.*

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Thus, under the prevailing environmental conditions the observed species composition of these benthos could be considered bio-indicators of organic pollution.

The ponds are not under any commercial use of fish culture though it has got potentiality and can bring the income and employment in the area through fish culture. The fish species may stocked as per the primary productivity of the ponds for utilization of fish culture which will also improve the water quality.

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